

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Wave 2 Questionnaire

User module "Sexual orientation"

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User Modules in the GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire

The GGS-II Wave 2 questionnaire was restructured to include new thematic sections, with space allocated for user-driven innovations. In 2023, an open call invited researchers to submit new content modules. The proposals were evaluated by a selection committee based on their scientific novelty and relevance to the GGS.

Five user modules were selected and integrated into the questionnaire, offering fresh insights into family dynamics, fertility, and related topics. This working paper series contains revised versions of the original submissions, including the finalized questions that were ultimately incorporated into the Wave 2 questionnaire.

Andersson, G., Neyer, G., Lappegård, T., & Bujard, M. (2024). *User module: "Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044105

Berrington, A., & Perelli-Harris, B. (2024). *User module: "Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044047

Billingsley, S., Mollborn, S., Olah, L., & Duvander, A.-Z. (2024). *User module: "Intensive Parenting"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14043910

Mortelmans, D., Lück, D., Claessens, E., Van Gasse, D., Bujard, M., & Frembs, L. (2024). *User module: "Singlehood"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044075

Rouvroye, L., Fischer, M., Rampazzo, F., van der Vleuten, M., Fortes De Lena, F., Pao, C., de Vries, L., & Jin, Y. (2024). *User module: "Sexual Orientation"* (GGS-II Wave 2 Questionnaire). GGP Working Paper Series. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14044062

Abstract

Within the scientific research community there is rapidly expanding awareness of sexual orientation as an important demographic characteristic shaping people's experiences, relationships, and opportunities throughout their lives. The inclusion of the selected survey module strengthens the GGS in three ways. First, it improves measurement precision regarding respondents' sexual orientation, which is relevant for research on partnership formation, relationship dynamics, fertility intentions, available pathways into family formation, and health status and well-being disparities. Second, it allows for research on outcomes in the family domain from a diversified life course perspective, creating the possibility to map different life-course trajectories for heterosexuals and sexual minority individuals. Third, it makes the GGS an attractive data source for a new community of researchers studying the sexual minority population, with additional potential for new insights through a cross-country comparative perspective. This module makes the GGS one of the first cross-national, longitudinal data sources for research on the LGBT+ community. The proposed questions on sexual orientation allow for better identification of members of the LGBT+ community among respondents to the GGS. These individuals are already in the data but are currently under- or misidentified due to lack of measures that accurately capture sexual orientation.

Motivation and scientific foundation

Scientific relevance and potential impact

Sexual orientation is an important social dimension that shapes laws, norms and institutions in our societies as well as individual life courses (Reçzek, 2020; Valfort, 2017). The inclusion of the selected questions provides numerous points of contact for new research, especially given the longitudinal design of the survey.

Possible research focuses are:

- Sexual minorities' desire to have children and obstacles to implementation.
- Division of housework and childcare in different family forms.
- Health status and well-being disparities between heterosexuals and sexual minorities.
- Composition of same-sex parent families (e.g. number and age of children, biological and adopted children, socio-demographics of parents).
- Partnership dynamics and gender roles of same-sex and different-sex partnerships.

Despite the marked relevance of research comparing the lives of heterosexuals and sexual minorities (Fischer et al., 2021) as well as among sexual minorities themselves (Van der Vleuten et al., 2021), longitudinal data sources are rare and there is currently no other cross-national longitudinal survey data source which allows this type of research. This presents a unique opportunity for the GGP to position itself at the forefront in the fields of demography and family sociology.

Demographic trends show that the number of people with same-sex partners and experiences is increasing over time (Kolk & Andersson, 2020; Lengerer & Bohr, 2019; Mishel et al., 2020). The growth in this segment of the population has implications for our understanding of processes such as union formation, the realisation of fertility intentions (i.e. family formation) and population ageing (Aldén et al., 2015; Evertsson, Jaspers & Moberg, 2020; Van der Vleuten et al., 2024). However, research aimed at studying partnership formation and dissolution over time requires data covering the preferences of the full population, not just couples (Reçzek, 2020). Since the number of cohabiting and married same-sex couples is on the rise, a growing number of children are and will be raised by same-sex parents (Digoix, 2020; Dimock et al., 2013; Evertsson et al., 2020; Evertsson & Boye, 2018; Kolk & Andersson, 2020). Precise measurement of people's sexual orientation facilitates prospective research on childrearing, independent from living with a partner of the same sex in a household as well as on the division of household work and paid labour in same-sex couples.

With the previous questionnaire, GGS respondents' sexual orientation could be approximated based on their answers to questions about their partnership history. However, this method has been criticized for being prone to errors (Régner-Loilier, 2018). Identification of same-sex couples via the household grid uses information on people's behaviour rather than their sexual identity. When only behavioural information is used to

infer people's sexual orientation, it results in the underrepresentation of this population, particularly in countries where sexual diversity is less visible and accepted (Fischer, 2016; Mishel, 2019). Moreover, a partnership-based method for the approximation of sexual orientation leaves single people without (previous) partnerships unidentified. It also does not identify bisexual people who are currently in a different-sex partnership. To sum this up, these pitfalls lead to non-coverage of a substantial part of the sexual minority population (Kühne, Kroh, Richter, 2019). Self-identification measures of sexual orientation increase measurement precision, also regarding desired partner choice and (preferred) couple composition. Such measures therefore improve the general quality of GGS data.

From a theoretical perspective, collecting information on people's sexual orientation and its role in their personal life history allows for family research from a diversified life course perspective. People's sexual orientation tends to shape their adolescent experiences (past), can partly explain their current relational circumstances (present) and has implications for their preferences and available opportunities in terms of family formation later in life (future) (Hammack et al. 2018; Ophir et al., 2023). Collecting information on GGS respondents' sexual orientation, including the timing of first attraction, allows for the mapping of differential life course trajectories of heterosexuals and sexual minority individuals. Comparing trajectories results in new theoretical insights, e.g., testing 'doing gender' approaches against rational choice motives for the division of household and paid labour in diverse couple types (Moberg & Van der Vleuten 2023; Van der Vleuten et al., 2021, 2024) or exploring aging trajectories and the experience of loneliness of single people by sexual orientation.

Research has shown structural inequality based on sexual orientation in all life domains, notably health (Buspavanich et al. 2021; Wittgens et al. 2022), social relationships (Fischer, 2021), intergenerational ties (Hank & Salzburger, 2015; Fischer & Kalmijn, 2020), family formation (Bos et al., 2008; Hank & Wetzel, 2018; Rijn-van Gelderen et al., 2015), and on the labour market (Aldén et al., 2015; Drydakis, 2019; Hammarstedt et al., 2015; Neumark, 2018; Valfort, 2017). In some of these domains, especially that of health, disadvantageous outcomes depend on the degree to which sexual minority people conceal or disclose information about their sexual orientation (Pachankis et. al., 2020). Gathering information on the concealment of sexual orientation among sexual minority respondents increases the GGS's potential for research on structural inequalities.

Methodological testing

The proposed sexual orientation question (*Sex01*) was tested extensively by the German Institute for Economic Research, Berlin before its implementation in the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) in 2016. Based on focus group feedback, the answer options do not only include identity labels, such as heterosexual or gay, but also an explanation in brackets. Older respondents were not always familiar with the identity labels and adding the explanation allowed all participants to answer the question without problems. Due to the inclusion of a "prefer not to say" option, the 2016 survey did not suffer from any notable drop out after the sexual orientation question. The question from SOEP was included in the German Family Demography Panel Study in 2022 with a small alteration

to the answer categories. The answer option “bisexual” was extended to “bisexual or pansexual” since this was the most frequent answer that people wrote down in the open answer category. The distinction between bisexual and pansexual may hold limited analytical significance in this context as both encompass attraction to more than one gender.

The proposed first attraction question (*Sex02*) is based on a question previously fielded by the Pew Research Center (2013) as part of the ‘Survey of LGBT Americans’. The original question has been adapted slightly to be suitable for all GGS respondents. This question can be used in life-course research as a retrospective measure for when LGBT+ respondents first realised their sexual orientation. The timing of this realisation can be compared to that among the heterosexual majority population.

The question on concealment of sexual orientation is taken from the Nebraska Outness Scale as put forward by Meidlinger and Hope (2014). Concealment of sexual orientation has been shown to be positively related to internalizing mental health problems (i.e., depression, anxiety, distress, problematic eating) (Pachankis et. al., 2020).

Relevance to GGS-II wave 2 and all countries

Sexual orientation is one key axis through which personal experiences and societal beliefs about partnerships, family norms and gender attitudes play out. Within the international research community there is growing awareness of the relevance of the intersection of sex, gender identity, and sexual orientation for contemporary population trends (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine, 2022). Various large-scale research data infrastructures, such as The German Family Demography Panel Study (FRoDA), the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) in Germany and the UK Census have recently included questions on sexual orientation. In its follow-up wave 2 survey, the GGP addresses diversity in gender identity, but questions addressing diversity in sexual attraction were still missing.

The inclusion of the proposed survey module ensures the GGP’s legacy as the flagship research data infrastructure on fertility, family dynamics and intergenerational relations. Furthermore, the GGP is one of the first cross-national, longitudinal data sources for research on the LGBT+ community. As a result, the GGP serves a new and growing community of researchers studying the sexual minority population.

Since inclusion of the proposed questions allows for better identification of members of the LGBT+ community within GGP respondents, this allows policy makers aiming to reduce societal inequalities to gain deeper insight into the experiences of the sexual minority population. To illustrate this point: within the Dutch country context, policy makers at the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (‘OCW – directie Emancipatie’) have inquired to what degree they could use GGS data to inform their work on the empowerment of the LGBT+ community.

The GGP's current core questionnaire clearly shows its aim to collect data on diverse family forms. The survey tries to refrain from a priori assumptions about people's lives and instead provides them with the opportunity to share their own experiences. We believe including the selected questions on sexual orientation greatly contributes to this aim. We are aware that some countries currently involved in the GGP might have reservations about including this module. However, we believe GGP's selection of the module on sexual orientation sends a clear signal to the international research community, namely that the GGP as a data infrastructure deems it important that everyone's life story is heard.

Survey questions

b5SEX01 (*Sexual orientation*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

In the context of relationships, the question of sexual orientation arises.

Would you say that you are...

Heterosexual (that is, attracted to the other gender)

Lesbian or gay (that is, attracted to the same gender as you)

Bisexual or pansexual (attracted to more than one gender)

Another orientation

IF (b5SEX01 = 4)

b5SEX01A (*Sexual orientation other*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Please describe your sexual orientation:

STRING

ENDIF

IF (b5SEX01 = 1)

b5SEX02A (*Sex02a*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to someone of the other gender?

If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.

NUMBER [0..100]

ENDIF

IF (b5SEX01 = 2)

b5SEX02B (*Sex02b*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to someone of the same gender as you?

If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.

NUMBER [0..100]

ENDIF

IF (b5SEX01 = 3)

b5SEX02C (*Sex02c*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to more than one gender?

If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.

NUMBER [0..100]

ENDIF

IF (((b5SEX01 = 2)OR(b5SEX01 = 3))OR(b5SEX01 = 4))

b5SEX03 (*Sex03*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How often do you avoid talking about topics related to or otherwise indicating your sexual orientation (e.g., not talking about your significant other, changing your mannerisms)?

Never

Rarely

Half of the time

Often

Always

ENDIF

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